

An efficient synthesis of 1,2-dihydro-1-aryl-3*H*-naphth[1,2-*e*][1,3]oxazin-3-one derivatives catalysed by 1,3-dibromo-5,5-dimethylhydantoin/kaolin under solvent-free conditions

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Abstract : A mild and efficient method has been developed for the preparation of 1,2-dihydro-1-aryl-3*H*-naphth[1,2-*e*][1,3]oxazin-3-one derivatives from the reaction of aromatic aldehydes with β -naphthol and urea in the presence of 1,3-dibromo 5,5-dimethylhydantoin (DBH), as an efficient, inexpensive catalyst under thermal and solvent-free conditions. Good yields, short reaction times, straightforward workup, and green conditions are the most obvious advantages of this procedure.

Keywords : 1,3-Dibromo-5,5-dimethylhydantoin, naphthoxazinones, solvent-free, one-pot reaction.

Introduction

Multicomponent reactions (MCRs) are of increasing importance in organic and medicinal chemistry, as high degrees of molecular diversity can be introduced by these reactions in a very fast, efficient, and time saving manner without the isolation of any intermediates. As a result, considerable attention has been paid to the development of new and improved one-pot multicomponent reactions in recent years¹. Driven by environmental concerns, the replacement of toxic organic solvents is one of the most important goals in *Green Chemistry*, which inevitably avoids solvent emission and waste².

Aromatic condensed oxazinone derivatives have received considerable attention due to the attractive pharmacological properties associated with their heterocyclic scaffold³. A thorough literature survey revealed that the compounds containing a dihydro-1,3-oxazine ring system exhibited a wide spectrum of pharmacological activities, such as antimicrobial⁴, HIV-1 reverse transcriptase inhibitors⁵, antiviral⁶, antibacterial⁷ and anti-inflammatory, analgesic and anthelmintic activity⁸. This class of heterocyclic compounds also act as PDGF receptor tyrosine kinase inhibitors⁹ and as potent 5-lipoxygenase inhibitors¹⁰. Dihydro-2*H*-1,4-benzoxazine-8-carboxamide hy-

drochloride were investigated as membrane receptors involved in modulation of responses of spinal dorsal horn interneurons evoked by Feline Group II muscle afferents¹¹. Some new tetrahydronaphtho[2,3-*b*][1,4]oxazine derivatives showed potent antihypertensive effects¹².

Some novel 2*H*-1,4-benzoxazine-3(4*H*)-one scaffold showed platelet fibrinogen receptor antagonists¹³. Some of the benzo[7,8]chromeno[5,6-*b*][1,4]oxazin-3-ones were tested for their ability to interact with DPPH, to compete with dimethylsulfoxide for hydroxyl radicals, to inhibit soybean lipoxygenase and trypsin activities *in vitro*¹⁴. Some new 1,4-benzoxazine derivatives act as potassium channel openers¹⁵. Moreover, 1,4-benzoxazine derivatives also showed immune modulating activity, immune response to *C. albicans*¹⁶. This class of heterocyclic compounds has also been used as precursors in the synthesis of phosphinic ligands for asymmetric catalysis¹⁷. Therefore, aromatic condensed oxazinone derivatives scaffold can be viewed as a 'privileged structure' among pharmaceutical compounds^{18,19}.

In spite of their importance from biological and synthetic points of view, Szatmari *et al.*²⁰ showed the synthesis of naphthoxazinones via condensation of aminoalkyl naphthols with phosgene in the presence of

triethylamine whereas Cimarelli and coworkers²¹ used carbonyl diimidazole instead of phosgene. Recently some other research groups have reported the synthesis of naphthoxazinones by the condensation of β -naphthol, aromatic aldehydes, and urea using various catalysts such as *p*-TSA²², phosphomolybdic acid²³, nanoparticulate copper in PEG-400²⁴, zinc oxide nanoparticle²⁵, micelle promoted supramolecular carbohydrate scaffold²⁶, $\text{RuCl}_2(\text{PPh}_3)_3$ ²⁷, nano silica supported ferric chloride²⁸, perchloric acid supported on silica ($\text{HClO}_4/\text{SiO}_2$)²⁹ and TiCl_4 ³⁰. However, some difficulties still exist, such as unsatisfactory yields, long reaction times, strong acidic conditions, highly expensive reagents. The required solvents or the reagents used are toxic and hazardous which causes environmental pollution. Therefore, development of simple, robust and safer methodologies for the synthesis of naphthoxazinone derivatives is of prime interest for obtaining these products under conditions tolerated by sensitive functional groups from both synthetic and environmental points of view.

1,3-Dibromo-5,5-dimethylhydantoin (DBH) is a five-membered heterocycle, which has recently gained special attention as an efficient homogeneous catalyst in various organic transformations^{31–36}. 1,3-Dibromo-5,5-dimethylhydantoin is used as an efficient catalyst for the synthesis of highly substituted furans³¹, 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2-(1*H*)-ones³², 2-arylthiazolines and 2-arylimidazolines³³, benzoxazoles, benzimidazoles, and oxazolo[4,5-*b*]pyridines³⁴, 14-aryl-14*H*-dibenzo[*a,j*]xanthenes³⁵ and polyhydro quinolines and 12-aryl-8,9,10,12-tetrahydro[*a*]-xanthene-11-ones³⁶.

Kaolin is natural substance that obtained from clay. It is a non-toxic substance and as a good ceramic material, it has the ability to withstand extreme heat and pressure. It is believed that kaolin has tremendous potential to be utilized as solid support material in both laboratory scale and industrial scale. Currently, strong interests in such natural supports were due to eco-friendly demands in many modern industrial applications³⁵.

Our group has been working extensively toward the development of new routes to the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds, novel methodologies under mild reaction conditions^{37–40}.

In this study, the convenient and practical synthesis of 1,2-dihydro-1-aryl-3*H*-naphth[1,2-*e*][1,3]oxazin-3-one derivatives via the simple and efficient, one-pot multi-component condensation reaction of aldehydes, β -naphthol and urea in the presence of a catalytic amount of DBH/kaolin under solvent-free condition was realized (Scheme 1). The products were synthesized in good to excellent yields and characterized by ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and mass spectroscopy, as well as by their physical constants.

Results and discussion

We report herein an efficient one-pot synthesis of 1,2-dihydro-1-aryl-3*H*-naphth[1,2-*e*][1,3]oxazin-3-one derivatives under solvent-free conditions from three components coupling of aromatic aldehydes, urea and β -naphthol in the presence of a catalytic amount of DBH/kaolin in excellent yield in short reaction time 40 min. For this purpose, as a model, the condensation of benzaldehyde

Scheme 1. Synthesis of 1,2-dihydro-1-aryl-3*H*-naphth[1,2-*e*][1,3]oxazin-3-one derivatives.

(1 mmol), urea (1.5 mmol) and β -naphthol (1 mmol) was examined in the presence of kaolin (100 mg) and DBH (10 mol%) as catalyst (Scheme 1).

In order to optimize the reaction conditions and to evaluate catalytic activity of DBH/kaolin, the model reaction was carried out under solvent-free conditions at 140 °C in presence of different catalysts, such as LiBr, CuBr₂, NiBr₂, *p*-TSA, HBF₄ and DBH to afford 1,2-dihydro-1-aryl-3*H*-naphth[1,2-*e*][1,3]oxazin-3-one **4a** (Table 1, entries 1–6). The optimized amount of the catalyst was determined using 0, 3, 5, 10 and 12 mol% of DBH under solvent-free conditions at 140 °C (Table 1,

was obtained in the absence of the catalyst (Table 1, entry 10).

Next, we focused on the solvent effects in different solvents such as EtOH, CH₂Cl₂, CH₃CN and DMF at reflux conditions (Table 1, entries 11–14). These results suggest that, in the presence of solvents under reflux conditions no product was formed. As revealed from Table 1, different temperatures could have a profound influence on the reaction rate. Various temperatures like, 100, 120, 130 and 140 °C were investigated (Table 1, entries 6 and 15–17). The yield of product was increased and reaction time was decreased with increasing in temperature and the highest yield in the shortest reaction time was obtained at 140 °C. Further increasing in the reaction temperature results decrease in the product yield (Table 1, entry 18).

Based on these results, it is clear that in the presence of kaolin (100 mg) and DBH (10 mol%) under solvent-free conditions at 140 °C is much more effective for the synthesis of 1,2-dihydro-1-aryl-3*H*-naphth[1,2-*e*][1,3]oxazin-3-ones in terms of reaction time and yield.

Moreover, the scope and efficiency of the catalyst was explored under the optimized reaction conditions. For this purpose, urea and β -naphthol were condensed with a broad range of structurally and electronically diverse aromatic aldehydes to produce the corresponding 1,2-dihydro-1-aryl-3*H*-naphth[1,2-*e*][1,3]oxazin-3-ones in high yields and short reaction times. The results are displayed in Table 2. The influence of electron-withdrawing and electron-donating substituents on the aromatic ring of aldehydes upon the reaction yields was investigated. The results showed that the reaction times slightly decreased but the yields increased in the presence of electron-withdrawing substituents.

Although the actual mechanism of the reaction is unclear, a reasonable explanation due to the high catalytic activity of DBH and mechanistic operation of DBH in similar reactions³⁸ is shown in Scheme 2. On the basis of this mechanism, DBH produces the bromonium cation (Br⁺) and activates the carbonyl group by the formation of oxygen cation (**a**). The reaction follows by the attack of urea (**2**) on the activated carbonyl of (**a**) to afford the formation of (**b**). Then the β -naphthol attacks on (**b**) to

Table 1. Optimization of the reaction conditions for the condensation of benzaldehyde, urea and β -naphthol^a

Entry	Catalyst	Condition	Time (min)	Yield (%) ^b
1	LiBr (10 mol%)	Solvent-free/140 °C	120	36
2	CuBr ₂ (10 mol%)	Solvent-free/140 °C	300	44
3	NiBr ₂ (10 mol%)	Solvent-free/140 °C	300	39
4	<i>p</i> -TSA (10 mol%)	Solvent-free/140 °C	300	47
5	HBF ₄ (10 mol%)	Solvent-free/140 °C	300	51
6	DBH (10 mol%)	Solvent-free/140 °C	40	93
7	DBH (12 mol%)	Solvent-free/140 °C	40	93
8	DBH (3 mol%)	Solvent-free/140 °C	90	55
9	DBH (5 mol%)	Solvent-free/140 °C	60	73
10	DBH (0 mol%)	Solvent-free/140 °C	300	14
11	DBH (10 mol%)	EtOH/Reflux	120	0
12	DBH (10 mol%)	CH ₂ Cl ₂ /Reflux	120	0
13	DBH (10 mol%)	CH ₃ CN/Reflux	120	0
14	DBH (10 mol%)	DMF/Reflux	120	0
15	DBH (10 mol%)	Solvent-free/100 °C	75	51
16	DBH (10 mol%)	Solvent-free/120 °C	60	66
17	DBH (10 mol%)	Solvent-free/130 °C	50	80
18	DBH (10 mol%)	Solvent-free/150 °C	40	88

^aReaction conditions : benzaldehyde (1 mmol), urea (1.5 mmol) and β -naphthol (1 mmol).

^bIsolated yield.

entries 6–10). As it can be seen in Table 1, 10 mol% of DBH catalyzes the reaction efficiently and produces high yield of the product in short reaction time (Table 1, entry 6). Increasing the amount of DBH to 12 mol% showed no substantial improvement in the yield (Table 1, entry 7), whereas the yield decreased by reducing the amount of the catalyst to 3 and 5 mol% (Table 1, entries 8–9). Moreover, it was observed that very less amount of yield

Table 2. Synthesis of various 1,2-dihydro-1-phenyl-naphtho-[1,2-*e*][1,3]oxazin-3-one derivatives^a

Entry	Aldehydes	Product	Time (min)	Yield (%) ^b
1	Benzaldehyde	4a	40	93
2	3-Fluoro benzaldehyde	4b	30	94
3	4-Methyl benzaldehyde	4c	50	88
4	4-Methoxy benzaldehyde	4d	50	89
5	3-Chloro benzaldehyde	4e	40	90
6	4-Nitro benzaldehyde	4f	30	92
7	4-Bromo benzaldehyde	4g	30	91
8	4-Fluoro benzaldehyde	4h	30	93
9	4- <i>N,N</i> -Dimethylamino benzaldehyde	4i	50	88
10	3-Nitro benzaldehyde	4j	40	90
11	3-Bromo benzaldehyde	4k	40	90
12	3-Methoxy benzaldehyde	4l	50	87

^aReaction conditions : aldehydes (1 mmol), urea (1.5 mmol) and β -naphthol (1 mmol) heating under solvent-free conditions at 140 °C in the presence of kaolin (100 mg) and DBH (10 mol%).

^bIsolated yield.

Scheme 2. Mechanism for the synthesis of 1,2-dihydro-1-aryl-3H-naphtho[1,2-*e*][1,3]oxazin-3-one derivatives.

generate (c). In the last step, the corresponding 1,2-dihydro-1-aryl-3H-naphtho[1,2-*e*][1,3]oxazin-3-one derivative is produced from (c) by releasing NH₃.

Experimental

Chemicals and analysis :

All commercial reagents were used as received without purification and all solvents were of reagent grade. The reaction was monitored by TLC using 0.25 mm Merck silica gel 60 F254 pre-coated plates, which were visualized with UV light. The melting points were determined in open capillaries. FT-IR spectra were obtained as KBr discs on Shimadzu spectrometer. ¹H NMR (500 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (125 MHz) spectra were obtained using Bruker DRX-500 Avance at ambient temperature, using TMS as internal standard. Mass spectra were determined on a Varion-Saturn 2000 GC/MS instrument. Elemental analysis were measured by means of Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHN elemental analyzer flowchart.

General experimental procedure :

A mixture of β -naphthol (1 mmol), aldehyde (1 mmol), urea (1.5 mmol), kaolin (100 mg) and DBH (10 mol%) was heated at 140 °C in oil bath for an appropriate time. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was diluted with dichloromethane (3 mL) and kaolin was filtrated. The solvent was evaporated under vacuum and the resulting solid products were recrystallized from ethanol. The products were found to be pure and no further purification was necessary.

Spectral data for the synthesized compounds :

*1,2-Dihydro-1-phenyl-naphtho[1,2-*e*][1,3]oxazin-3-one (4a)* :

White powder; m.p. 217–219 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3277, 3155, 1715, 1594, 866, 713; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 6.11 (1H, s, CH), 7.11–7.21 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.39–7.50 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.67–7.80 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.77 (1H, s, NH) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 53.7, 114.1, 117.9, 123.4, 125.7, 127.0, 127.5, 128.0, 128.7, 129.2, 129.7, 130.2, 130.6, 143.3, 146.7, 148.9 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 276 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₃NO₂ : C, 78.55; H, 4.72; N, 5.09%. Found : C, 78.56; H, 4.66; N, 5.05%.

*1,2-Dihydro-1-(3-fluorophenyl)naphtho[1,2-*e*][1,3]oxazin-3-one (4b)* :

White powder; m.p. 218–220 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3274, 3152, 1711, 1603, 863, 711; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 6.14 (1H, s, CH), 7.07–7.19 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.44–7.53 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.64–7.83 (4H, m, Ar-H),

8.73 (1H, s, NH) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 54.0, 113.6, 117.3, 123.7, 125.0, 126.9, 127.6, 128.2, 128.8, 129.1, 129.6, 130.3, 130.9, 142.8, 147.0, 149.5 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 294 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₂FNO₂ : C, 73.72; H, 4.10; N, 4.78%. Found : C, 73.61; H, 4.03; N, 4.74%.

*1,2-Dihydro-1-(4-methylphenyl)naphtho[1,2-*e*][1,3]oxazin-3-one (4c)* :

White powder; m.p. 167–169 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3269, 3147, 1709, 1597, 856, 722; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 2.17 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.13 (1H, s, CH), 7.12 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.24 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.47–7.55 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.68–7.88 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.70 (1H, s, NH) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 21.5, 53.8, 114.0, 117.5, 123.8, 125.6, 126.8, 127.7, 128.0, 128.6, 129.0, 129.5, 130.1, 130.5, 142.7, 146.8, 149.3 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 290 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₅NO₂ : C, 78.89; H, 5.19; N, 4.84%. Found : C, 78.83; H, 5.12; N, 4.86%.

*1,2-Dihydro-1-(4-methoxyphenyl)naphtho[1,2-*e*][1,3]oxazin-3-one (4d)* :

White powder; m.p. 184–186 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3268, 3143, 1718, 1606, 857, 725; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 3.67 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.21 (1H, s, CH), 7.02 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.18 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.46–7.57 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.67–7.85 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.76 (1H, s, NH) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 53.9, 54.6, 113.7, 117.2, 124.1, 125.2, 127.4, 127.9, 128.3, 128.5, 129.3, 129.7, 130.3, 130.7, 143.0, 147.3, 148.7 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 306 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₅NO₃ : C, 74.75; H, 4.92; N, 4.59%. Found : C, 74.70; H, 4.94; N, 4.52%.

*1,2-Dihydro-1-(3-chlorophenyl)naphtho[1,2-*e*][1,3]oxazin-3-one (4e)* :

White powder; m.p. 193–195 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3271, 3153, 1704, 1595, 860, 721; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 6.12 (1H, s, CH), 7.09–7.21 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.40–7.53 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.70–7.93 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.80 (1H, s, NH) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 53.6, 114.2, 118.0, 124.2, 126.0, 127.2, 127.8, 128.1, 128.6, 129.4, 129.8, 130.4, 130.9, 142.6, 146.9, 149.0 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 310 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₂ClNO₂ : C, 69.80; H, 3.88; N, 4.52%. Found : C, 69.73; H, 3.86; N, 4.51%.

*1,2-Dihydro-1-(4-nitrophenyl)naphtho[1,2-*e*][1,3]oxazin-3-one (4f)* :

White powder; m.p. 188–190 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3272, 3149, 1707, 1608, 857, 714; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 6.20 (1H, s, CH), 7.01 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.20 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.38–7.49 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.71–7.89 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.82 (1H, s, NH) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 54.2, 113.9, 118.1, 123.6, 125.6, 127.3, 127.6, 128.3, 128.7, 129.1, 129.7, 130.3, 130.5, 143.3, 147.0, 148.8 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 321 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₂N₂O₄ : C, 67.50; H, 3.75; N, 8.75%. Found : C, 67.44; H, 3.74; N, 8.77%.

*1,2-Dihydro-1-(4-bromophenyl)naphtho[1,2-*e*][1,3]oxazin-3-one (4g)* :

White powder; m.p. 220–222 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3266, 3141, 1724, 1603, 862, 721; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 6.17 (1H, s, CH), 7.10 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.18 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.46–7.54 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.66–7.80 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.85 (1H, s, NH) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 53.6, 114.4, 117.5, 123.8, 126.1, 127.0, 127.7, 128.2, 128.8, 129.2, 129.8, 130.2, 130.7, 142.9, 146.7, 149.5 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 355 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₂BrNO₂ : C, 61.03; H, 3.39; N, 3.96%. Found : C, 61.00; H, 3.33; N, 3.91%.

*1,2-Dihydro-1-(4-fluorophenyl)naphtho[1,2-*e*][1,3]oxazin-3-one (4h)* :

White powder; m.p. 203–205 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3265, 3157, 1720, 1599, 855, 709; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 6.10 (1H, s, CH), 7.03 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.17 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.40–7.48 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.67–7.81 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.78 (1H, s, NH) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 53.9, 113.8, 117.7, 123.4, 125.4, 126.8, 127.5, 128.0, 129.0, 129.5, 129.9, 130.5, 130.9, 143.5, 147.3, 149.6 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 294 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₂FNO₂ : C, 73.72; H, 4.10; N, 4.78%. Found : C, 73.67; H, 4.11; N, 4.77%.

*1,2-Dihydro-1-(4-*N,N*-dimethylaminophenyl)-naphtho[1,2-*e*][1,3]oxazin-3-one (4i)* :

White powder; m.p. 216–218 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3271, 3160, 1713, 1597, 854, 707; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 3.06 (6H, s, N(CH₃)₂), 6.14 (1H, s, CH), 7.09 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.24 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.44–7.54 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.71–7.82 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.80 (1H, s, NH) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃)

δ : 40.6, 54.3, 114.3, 117.8, 124.2, 125.8, 126.9, 127.6, 128.2, 129.1, 129.7, 129.9, 130.2, 130.6, 142.7, 146.9, 149.4 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 317 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₈N₂O₂ : C, 75.47; H, 5.66; N, 8.81%. Found : C, 79.66; H, 6.24; N, 8.82%.

1, 2-Dihydro-1-(3-nitrophenyl)naphtho[1, 2-e][1,3]oxazin-3-one (4j) :

White powder; m.p. 210–212 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3263, 3152, 1715, 1604, 859, 715; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 6.19 (1H, s, CH), 7.07–7.18 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.39–7.50 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.63–7.81 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.74 (1H, s, NH) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 54.1, 113.6, 117.9, 124.0, 125.9, 127.3, 127.9, 128.3, 129.0, 129.3, 129.7, 130.0, 130.5, 142.8, 146.8, 149.6 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 321 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₂N₂O₄ : C, 67.50; H, 3.75; N, 8.75%. Found : C, 67.38; H, 3.68; N, 8.70%.

1, 2-Dihydro-1-(3-bromophenyl)naphtho[1, 2-e][1,3]oxazin-3-one (4k) :

White powder; m.p. 231–233 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3268, 3147, 1714, 1602, 863, 718; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 6.12 (1H, s, CH), 7.12–7.23 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.41–7.48 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.69–7.84 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.81 (1H, s, NH) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 53.7, 114.4, 117.6, 123.8, 125.7, 127.1, 127.7, 128.4, 128.9, 129.3, 129.8, 130.1, 130.7, 142.7, 147.4, 148.9 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 354.9 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₂BrNO₂ : C, 61.03; H, 3.39; N, 3.96%. Found : C, 60.96; H, 3.37; N, 3.97%.

1, 2-Dihydro-1-(3-methoxyphenyl)naphtho[1, 2-e][1,3]oxazin-3-one (4l) :

White powder; m.p. 201–203 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3274, 3143, 1721, 1605, 857, 721; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 3.64 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.15 (1H, s, CH), 7.10–7.24 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.40–7.47 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.73–7.85 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.79 (1H, s, NH) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 54.0, 114.2, 117.5, 123.7, 125.6, 127.2, 127.8, 128.2, 129.0, 129.3, 129.7, 130.2, 130.8, 143.0, 147.5, 149.2 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 306 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₅NO₃ : C, 74.75; H, 4.92; N, 4.59%. Found : C, 74.64; H, 4.88; N, 4.57%.

Conclusions

In conclusion, we have developed an easy, efficient

and eco-friendly procedure for the one-pot synthesis of 1,2-dihydro-1-aryl-3*H*-naphth[1,2-*e*][1,3]oxazin-3-one via a multicomponent reaction of aldehydes, urea with β -naphthol using DBH, a homogeneous catalyst under solvent free conditions. The mildness of the conversion, experimental simplicity, compatibility with various functional groups, high yields of the reaction product, shorter reaction times and the easy workup procedure, etc., makes this procedure attractive to synthesize a variety of these derivatives.

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